

Tsallis Entropy and a Conservation of Energy Scheme

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In (1), it is noted that Tsallis entropy is associated with a special $\ln_q(x)$ function defined as: $\{x^{\text{power}(1-q)} - 1\} / (1-q)$. This may be obtained (as noted in (1)) from: $\int (1, x) ds / (s^{\text{power} q})$. In the case of $q=1$, one obtains the usual \ln function (linked with a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.)

In this note, we wish to find a systematic approach, linked to two body elastic scattering which holds for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases and the Tsallis case. Our main approach is to note that in the Maxwell-Boltzmann approach, $f_1 f_2 = f_3 f_4$ with $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$, one may take the \ln of the first equation and equate it to the second. An alternative is to take a differential of the first equation and then divide by itself. This seems to lead to a more general scheme that does not require the explicit use of a \ln function and so is applicable to the Tsallis case as well as the MB one (and Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein as well).

Motivation

In (1) and other treatments of Tsallis entropy, a generalized logarithm function $\ln_q(x)$ is introduced as:

$$\ln_q(x) = \{x^{\text{power}(1-q)} - 1\} / (1-q) \quad ((1))$$

In the case of $q=1$, using q as the variable together with l'Hopital's rule, yields $\ln(x)$. $\ln(x)$ is known to appear in the Maxwell-Boltzmann approach. For example, if $x=f(e)$ (probability for a single particle with energy e , then $\ln(f)$ is information.

Here, we wish to find a generalized scheme, linked with conservation of energy in two particle scattering, which applies to the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases as well as the Tsallis scenario.

Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) Distribution and Elastic Two Body Scattering

We begin by obtaining the MB distribution by considering elastic two body scattering. In such a case:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad f(e_1) f(e_2) = f(e_3) f(e_4) \quad ((2b))$$

A standard approach is to take the \ln of ((2b)), multiply it by a constant and equate each term to ((2a)).

Formally, however, there is no reason to use the \ln function. There exists an alternative which separates the factors in ((2b)), namely taking a differential and then dividing by the function

itself. This leads to relative probabilities. We suggest that this second approach is readily generalizable to the Tsallis scenario.

$$\text{Thus, } df(e_1)/f(e_1) + df(e_2)/f(e_2) = df(e_3)/f(e_3) + df(e_4)/f(e_4) \quad ((3))$$

One may then obtain $\ln(f)$, the information, by integrating:

$$\ln(f) = \int (1/f) ds/s \quad ((4)) \quad (\text{This integral with } s \text{ power } q \text{ is introduced in (1).})$$

We first try to generalize this MB approach, using differentials, to the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases.

Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein Cases

For these cases, one may use conservation of energy again:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((4a))$$

$$f(e_1)\{1 \mp f(e_3)\} f(e_2)\{1 \mp f(e_4)\} = f(e_3)\{1 \mp f(e_1)\} f(e_4)\{1 \mp f(e_2)\} \quad ((4b))$$

The minus applies to the Fermi-Dirac case and the + to the Bose-Einstein. In order to take differentials, it is convenient to group all $f(e_i)$ variables together, i.e.

$$\{f(e_1)/\{1 \mp f(e_1)\}\} \{f(e_2)/\{1 \mp f(e_2)\}\} = \{f(e_3)/\{1 \mp f(e_3)\}\} \{f(e_4)/\{1 \mp f(e_4)\}\} \quad ((5))$$

Now, as in the MB case, one may take \ln of both sides of ((5)) or differentials and then divide by the full function on each side of ((5)). This leads to terms of the form:

$$d \{ f(e_i) / (1 \mp f(e_i)) \} / \{ f(e_i) / (1 \mp f(e_i)) \} \quad ((6))$$

This is now a more generalized kind of relative probability and is linked with:

$$d \ln \{ f(e_i) / (1 \mp f(e_i)) \} \quad ((7a))$$

Thus, we see that one may have the notion of conservation of energy in two body scattering, but information is a little different than simply $\ln(f)$. We also see the emergence of:

$$G(f(e_1)) G(f(e_2)) = G(f(e_3)) G(f(e_4)) \quad ((7b))$$

We now try to generalize once more for the Tsallis case.

Tsallis Case

In (1), the Tsallis case is described by modifying the MB case:

$\ln(f) = \int (1, f) ds / s \quad ((8))$ to

$\ln_q(f) = \int (1, f) ds / s^q \quad ((9)).$

We wish to see how ((9)) arises through the differential approach described above for the MB and FD, BE cases. We begin with conservation of energy and a special function $G(f)$ such that:

$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((10a))$ and $G(f(e_1))G(f(e_2)) = G(f(e_3))G(f(e_4)) \quad ((10b))$

We then impose the restriction:

$dG/G = d \ln(G) = f^{-q} df \quad ((11))$

This means that one should modify $\int (1, f) ds/s$ to:

$\int (1, f) ds / s^q$ which yields $\{f^{1-q} - 1\} / (1-q) \quad ((12))$

Alternatively, one may see that: $\ln G = f^{1-q} / (1-q) + \text{constant}$ directly from ((11)).

Thus, the differential approach to finding information seems to be a consistent one which holds for the MB, FD, BE and Tsallis cases in a consistent manner. One need only introduce the restriction ((11)) which defines the Tsallis scenario.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to introduce a generalized approach which yields information not only in the MB, FD and BE cases, but also in the Tsallis case. We first note that in the MB case, two body elastic scattering: $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ and $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$ usually leads to one taking \ln of the second equation and equating to the first to obtain the MB (Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution). An alternative approach, which may be generalized, however, is to take differentials of the second equation and then divide by the function itself. This leads to terms of the form $df(e_i)/f(e_i)$ which may be integrated to yield information $\ln(f(e_i))$. We have shown that this approach may be applied to the FD and BE cases. Our real interest, however, is to apply it to the Tsallis case which we do by imposing the restriction $dG/G = f^{-q} df$. In this case, instead of $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$ one has $G(f(e_1))G(f(e_2)) = G(f(e_3))G(f(e_4))$. One then seeks a solution of $\ln(G)$ which is $f^{1-q}/(1-q) + \text{constant}$. One may fix the constant such that $q=1$ yields the \ln function or integrate $\int (1, f) ds / s^q$ as in (1).

References

1. Okamura, K. Emergent Families of Tsallis Entropies from the q -deformed combinatorics (Sept. 28, 2024) <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2407.11257>